

The Coupling Constant Equation and Pauli Exclusion Principle – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

The following is an analysis of the Pauli Exclusion Principle, taken from a new standpoint of the coupling constant equation and the new framework 8-theory. Theory that combined general relativity with QM, by extrapolation of the coupling constant series using a Lorentz manifold. This paper will examine the anti-commutation relation of fermions, and analyze the reason behind electrons repelling each other.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

We have seen that we can change the term outside the parenthesis, and so we can reach duality between the forces. When we did it in the first three terms, we saw that their duality is exactly on 24+2 variations, which is in agreement with what we know in other theories of GUT. We briefly mention in that paper, that we cannot touch the invariant (3).

This will be the subject of this paper. If we for example combine:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \pm \text{INTEGER} \dots \quad (2)$$

We can switch and change the terms outside the parenthesis, as those are net variations and they do not seem to obey to any strict rules. However, we could not touch the invariant (3) and now we will examine deeply the reason.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3) + (3)] + 5 = [(24 * 5) + \text{Even}] + 5 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Even} = 0$$

$$[(24 * 5) + 0] + 5 \rightarrow \text{Impossible} \quad (4)$$

As even amount of variations vanish. Remember that the invariant (3) is the cause; It is the destabilizing factor yielding a net variation. In the case of the third element, it is the Electron. So using that framework, we can see why we cannot combine 2 electrons or invariant (3) Elements together.

The term than becomes meaningless, a photon cannot propagate from nowhere and the coupling constant series does not makes sense anymore. So the invariant (3) cannot be combined, it will repel each other. The net variation however can be changed and switched, which makes the Flexibility and duality of the forces. The equation is with complete agreement with our understanding; we are just examining additional Meaning of it. It allows us to examine it from a deeper, more profound view. Now we can understand why fermions do not commute – because even variations vanish and so bosons will not be propagated. If we eliminate the electron, than no boson will be propagate at all. However, consider the following:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + \dots \quad (5)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + \dots \quad (6)$$

While we cannot touch the terms inside the parenthesis, we can change and combine the net Variation, there seems to be no limitation in regards to that operation, we have done it before, and showed that the forces can be scalar multiples. We can cluster the net variations, which means that many electrons can emit net variations together, That is bosons, which agrees to what we know as laser, or what we know as bosons commutation Relation in QFT. However, using the 8-theory framework we can get a new and fresh insight on why those things are the way they are using the coupling constant equation. As we mentioned in part four of the paper series on coupling constants, the invariant (3) blends in the total cluster of the fermions, so we cannot know where he is. That is in agreement with the Heisenberg principle of uncertainty.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)